

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B416
 Date: 07 Nov 2008
 Take Off: 10:32:20
 Landing: 15:27:26
 Flight Time 4h 55m 06s

Campaign: VOCALS – POC Flight 3

Operating Area: S.E. Pacific Ocean off the coast of northern Chile

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Phil Brown	Met Office	
6	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
7	Core Chem / AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
11	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
12	CAPS / 2DS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
13	AMS	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
14	Wet Neph / PSAP / Filters	James Bowles	Met Office	
15	VACC	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
16	Mission Scientist 3	Alan Gadian	Leeds University	
17	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
18	MARSS	Jeff Norwood Brown	Met Office	
19				

Flight Track:

B416 Track 07-NOV-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B416

Date: 7 November 2008

Project: VOCALS

Location: Pacific off coast of northern Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
100433		gin	0.08 kft	021	on
102749		ASP	0.07 kft	020	open
103220		T/O	0.05 kft	199	Arica
103220	105826	Profile 1	0.24 - 22.0 kft	199	
103613		!	2.8 kft	249	cloud base 2500
103749		!	4.3 kft	251	cloud top fl 038 / 3900ft
103903		nev	5.4 kft	252	zero
103959		TW	6.0 kft	249	zero
105826	120301	Run 1	22.0 - 12.8 kft	251	
105914		Sonde 1	22.1 kft	251	
110627		Sonde 2	22.0 kft	258	
110830		heimann	22.0 kft	243	cal06
111429		Sonde 3	22.0 kft	252	
112224		sonde 4	22.0 kft	253	
113027		sonde 5	22.0 kft	253	
115400	121030	Profile 2	12.8 - 4.9 kft	241	
121030	123108	Run 2	4.9 - 5.0 kft	242	
121320		!	4.9 kft	085	start run
121407		!	4.9 kft	071	ref S20 03.18 W 077 32.23
121437		!	4.9 kft	070	5000ft qnh 1016
121506		!	5.0 kft	068	rad 5100ft
121842		nev	5.0 kft	062	zero check
121851		TW	5.0 kft	060	zero check
123109	123521	Profile 3	5.0 - 0.91 kft	049	
123229		!	4.2 kft	323	cloud tops 4300
123333		!	2.9 kft	327	cloud base 3000
123521	125529	Run 3	0.91 - 0.86 kft	241	
123614		!	0.93 kft	242	qnh 1019
123810		psap	0.81 kft	242	flow off - drizzle
124014		jw	0.87 kft	230	zero
124119		heimann	0.91 kft	234	cal09
125036		!	0.83 kft	240	1246 sudden jump of 5C in thermometer readings
125123		!	0.86 kft	240	1061ft (radar)
125540	125759	Profile 4	0.89 - 2.9 kft	252	
125759	132004	Run 4	2.9 - 3.7 kft	047	
125842		R4	3.1 kft	049	interrrupted climbing
125949		R4	3.8 kft	051	resumed
130007		!	3.8 kft	055	cvi reports no TAS
130552		!	3.8 kft	051	port aft dlu reset (locked up)
132105	132221	Profile 5	3.7 - 4.8 kft	310	
132221	134225	Run 5	4.8 - 2.6 kft	247	Sawtooth run, descendind start
132611		!	0.89 kft	245	sawtooth reversal V -> ^
133054		!	4.9 kft	245	sawtooth reversal ^ -> V
133527		!	0.86 kft	247	sawtooth reversal V -> ^
134026		!	4.8 kft	243	sawtooth reversal ^ -> V
134325		!	2.0 kft	084	manouvre
134422	140742	Profile 6	0.87 - 23.0 kft	083	
140743	145920	Run 6	23.0 kft	088	
140752		Sonde 6	23.0 kft	090	
141543		Sonde 7	23.0 kft	087	
142344		Sonde 8	23.0 kft	085	
143144		Sonde 9	23.0 kft	081	
144115		Sonde 10	23.1 kft	078	
144806		Sonde 11	22.9 kft	087	
145920	152726	Profile 7	23.0 - 0.04 kft	074	to land
152726		Land	0.06 kft	201	Arica
153001		ASP	0.04 kft	020	closed

B416 Track 07-NOV-08

Pilot: Alan Foster

NavData Cycle 2008-11 Expires: Thursday, 20 November 2008.

Scale: 1:4584494 (1 inch = 62.88 naut mi). Printed on 06 Nov 2008

7 6 9 9 6 ; 6 8

FliteStar 9.4.2.0

FAAM Sortie, Flight B416 - VOCALS POC mission 3 - Draft 1
Fri 7th November 2008

T/O - 0730 local (1030 UTC).
Land - 1245 local (1545 UTC)

Mission Scientists: Keith Bower, Phil Brown, Alan Gadian

Operating Area: SE Pacific Ocean, off west coast of northern Chile, point Zulu

Waypoints: point ZULU: 77°W 20.5°S (approx 2hrs on mission)

NB ZULU should be at the boundary of a POC; if necessary this point can be repositioned within box defined by 75-80°W 18°20'-22°S.

Note that if point ZULU is 80°W longitude then add approx 30 mins to transit time.

Sortie Objectives: To measure the dynamics, microphysical and large-scale structure, chemistry and processes of a cluster of closed convective cells (a.k.a. Pockets of Open Cells - POCS) embedded in marine stratocumulus off the West Coast of Chile.

Latest satellite Image (to be inserted):

Detailed Flight schedule: PTO

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – as per instructions.

ARIES – as per instructions

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode : **AMS** and **SMPS** to sample from it

Wet Neph – operated during all of low level non-cloud runs

AMS – operate from Rosemount during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; operate on CVI during in cloud runs

Filters – Vent the inlet line in the absence of filter immediately after cloud run prior to starting filter run for between 2 and 5 minutes. 2x filters on sub-cloud leg. 1 either side of boundary.

Flight Summary:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to FL230
2. Transit towards point ZULU, dropping a total of 5 sondes. [T1 mins]
3. Profile descent at 1000 ft/min to reach point ZULU at 5000 ft (or above cloud). [18 min; T1+18min]
4. Fly a 20 minute leg above cloud crossing the boundary between the POC and surrounding overcast Sc drifting with the mean wind. [20 min; T1+38min]
4. Descend and turn 180 degrees to 1000 ft (or just below cloud) within the POC and fly a 30-minute run from clear air towards the overcast Sc (POC boundary at the mid-point of the run) drifting with the mean wind [30 min; T1+68 min]
5. Ascend and turn 180 degrees to 3000 ft (or to an altitude within cloud) and fly a 30-minute run at cloud level starting in overcast Sc and heading into POC (POC boundary at the mid-point of the run) drifting with the mean wind [30 min; T1+98 min]
6. Continue legs across boundary as defined by mission scientist (possibly saw tooth leg) as time permits [40 min; T1+138min].
7. Turn to Arica recovery radial and descend to minimum safe altitude and perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min to FL 100, followed by a climb to FL 230. [15 min; T1+153 min].
8. High level recovery to Arica (FL 230) dropping a total of 5 sondes. [T2; T=315 min].

NB to ensure the success of this mission it is essential that current satellite images can be received on the aircraft and it would be useful to have communications via x-chat with Mission Scientists on the ground.

FAAM Flight B416 (VOCALS POC mission #3) (07/11/2008)
Mission Scientist Debrief : Keith N Bower

Mission Scientists: Keith Bower, Phil Brown, Alan Gadian

Sortie Objectives: To measure the dynamics, microphysical and large-scale structure, chemistry and processes of a cluster of closed convective cells (a.k.a. Pockets of Open Cells - POCs) embedded in marine stratocumulus off the West Coast of Chile

Operating Area: SE Pacific Ocean, off west coast of northern Chile, point Zulu

Waypoints: initial point ZULU: 77°W 20.5°S (approx 2hrs on mission)

Takeoff : 1032utc

Landing : 15:27utc

Mission summary

Take-off from Arica at 10:32UTC was the start of profile ascent P1 (at 1000ft/min) to FL220 heading for new point Zulu (20S 77.5W – determined from latest Satellite picture). On this ascent cloud base and cloud top (CB and CT) were seen to be around 2500 and 3900feet respectively (on pressure setting of 1013mbar). Below cloud it was very hazy and there was a full stratocumulus (8/8) deck. Above the inversion at 850mbar (4kft) there was a band of increased wetness between 800 and 750mbar (7-8kft) also identified by the nephelometers as a layer of increased scattering. At the end of the profile, 5 dropsondes were dropped at 8 minute intervals. The last of these had late reporting of winds. Prior to this at around 19S 72W a small amount of Ci was observed to the south of us, but little ahead. A large (closed) rift-like structure could be seen ahead of us upon crossing 74W – this shows up on the 10:58utc satellite image (Figure 1) as a feature running from the NW to SE crossing through 20S 75W, and seems to be associated with the margins between full maritime and coastally influenced airmasses. This view seemed to be supported by the thermodynamic data observed.

Closer to arriving at point Zulu, nearing 20S 77W a few features could be seen ahead in the cloud layer (see photograph in Figure 2 below). These consisted of a line of small Cu cloudtops joined by rift like dark patches in the distance, with a line of similar features slightly closer to our position. These were believed to be the POC-like features observed in the satellite picture, and so a decision was taken to profile down towards these to consider how best to work the features. At 14.5kft the feature was sufficiently clear to decide to carry out legs across it on headings of 240 and 60 degrees. In order to complete the required above cloud, below cloud, in cloud level straight and level runs (SLRs) and a saw tooth run through the boundary layer, transect lengths shortened to 20 minutes each centred on the POC boundary were planned (NB the mission length had to be reduced by 30mins as the status for insurance cover for using Tacna as the diversion airfield was not known, so less time was available on station because of the use of Iquique as the diversion

airfield). The Captain determined that the midpoint of the first of these transect legs should be at 20deg 3.18min S and 77deg 32.23min W.

Figure 1 : Satellite image (visible) at 10:58utc showing the feature of interest at 77.5W 20S

Figure 2 : A early view of the feature to be investigated during mission B416 in the distance

The first run across the rift-like feature (R2) was carried out above CT at 5000ft (p setting 1016mbar), although some Cu tops could be seen through the Sc CT on the left hand side. It was clear that the rift feature had not evolved back to the stage of having opened up to form a POC, but nevertheless, it possessed many of the features observed on previous POC flights (ie it was probably a POC which had filled in and retained POC like characteristics). CCN/CN concentrations (cm⁻³) changed from 30 (at 0.1% supersaturation)/200 to around 15/200 to 240. The adapted (removing the anomalous Ch1 counts and filling the Ch1 gap with Ch2 concentrations) PCASP counts fell from ~240 to around 125 cm⁻³ over the region.

At the end of R2 (NE end) a profile descent P3 to 1000ft amsl (p setting 1019mbar) was undertaken. The decision was also taken to drift with the wind to move transects further to the NW (mean winds on profile were around 8-10m/s at approx 150deg). During P3, CT and Sc CB were reported at 4300ft and 3000ft respectively. On the reciprocal below cloud run, R3 (at 1000ft) Cu cloud bases as low 1200ft were observed. Prior to reaching the rift boundary (under the main Sc deck) the number of CCN was higher (CCN/CN = 50/230). A little drizzle (< 10 drops per litre) was observed by the 2DS (drops ~250um in size) and 2DC (500um). As R3 progressed more drizzle was seen in another burst. The boundaries of the rift/POC edge were not obvious by sight, but after 12 min the aircraft flew below a small opening in the Sc deck (coinciding with more light drizzle!). CN decreased by 150 cm⁻³ and CCN decreased dramatically too. O₃ was reported to have experienced a large decrease while a more moderate decrease in CO was reported. CN concentrations were now 30 cm⁻³. At this point the problem with some core data discontinuities/issues distracted observations (eg T and theta increased by 6 deg in one jump, updraughts apparently increased by +3 m/s etc – but none of this was considered real). Meanwhile, towards the end of R3, CCN decreased to 10 cm⁻³ while CN dropped more modestly from 250 to 200 cm⁻³.

At the end of R3 (SW extreme) a profile ascent up to initially 3000ft was carried out to begin an in-cloud run. However, 3000ft put the run into the Cu turrets but only just at the bottom of the main Sc deck. Following a brief ascent, R4 was carried out in cloud at 3900feet. Initially CAS reported 300 drops cm⁻³ at a mean size of 15um, while core cloud reported 230 cm⁻³ at the same size. After a couple of minutes, LWC increased, and CCN reported zero counts. A lot of drizzle was also reported. Core cloud reported CDP droplet concentrations had fallen to 20 cm⁻³ with a mean diameter of 35um. The FSSP saw around 30 drops at 28um. 2DC reported ~1000/litre of drizzle drops at around 150um. The CDP and FSSP then saw a gradual decrease in mean drop size to around 20 and 18um, while concentrations recovered to around 100 and 150 cm⁻³ respectively. Observations from CAS were in agreement too, while 2DC concentrations also fell.

At the end of R4 in-cloud (NE end), R5 was carried out as a so-called “saw-tooth” run consisting of series of profiles (at 1000ft/min) up to 5000ft (above CT and the inversion) and then down to 1000ft amsl through the cloud deck (ending up below all cloud bases). The main observation from this series of profile ascents and descents was that CT was consistently around 4500ft at the NE end of the run maybe decreasing slightly by 300ft towards the SW end of the run. Above this altitude there was a strong inversion

consisting of very dry and warmer air. CBs of the main Sc cloud were around 3000ft, with the Cu bases descending to as low as 2000ft. At the start of R5 it was noticeable that the Nevzorov total water was in close agreement with the J-W, while earlier this wasn't true when drizzle concentrations were higher. There were nice peaks in drizzle concentrations at the top of a couple of the CT profile segments.

At the end of this series of transects across the boundaries of this rift/POC feature, a profile ascent P6 from 1000ft amsl back up to the transit level of FL230 was carried out, heading back up through the region. This indicated an extremely stable profile. Once at FL230 a further 6 drop sondes were dropped at 8 minute intervals. Profile P6 also revealed a layer of enhanced ozone concentrations between 5000 and 10000ft, with peak concentrations of >45ppb observed. There was a corresponding maximum in CO in the same layer (max ~73ppb) with a possible correlation with NO_x too although concentrations of the latter were very low. R6 at FL230 also showed the transition once again between the maritime and coastal air mass boundary in the thermodynamic data. Finally profile P7 was carried out from FL230 down to ground level upon return to Arica. The aircraft landed at Arica at 15:27z.

Instrumentation

CVI : CPC now on the CVI.

Wet-Neph, Neph and PSAP OK

SWS/ARIES/MARSS : good throughout except for SWS at start of profile P1

SHIM : upper OK lower not working

AMS : fine

SMPS : OK

Core chemistry ; CO NO_x SO₂ all fine, O₃ leak from cabin on "capped" port discovered and probably corrected. Some of highest O₃ concentrations observed for a while in profile P6

CCN : one channel only, Water CPC : fine throughout flight

VACC : ok – not much to measure

Cloud microphysics:

PCASP : Ch 1 which suffers high counts removed from distribution, replaced by Ch 2 values to make spectrum and total numbers more believable

Backup FSSP and CDP OK

CIP-15 (remains faulty)

LWC JW and Nevzorov : good.

2DS : fine

CAPS : fine

Filters – fine

Drop sondes – aqll good except one reported late winds.

Jump in T and theta noted at 12:50, CVI noted not getting a TAS. TAS data error potential cause, IAS. Reset RSVM at 13:05. Instruments using IAS as input in calculation of parameters will have been affected – those using IAS post flight should be OK

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Flight B416 10:44:37
Heading 246 deg Speed 236 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb
Lat 18°36.0'S Long 71°0.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 275 deg
Temp 12.49C Dewpoint -29.45C

Track Plot Plot From: 10:33 To: now -

Save plot parameters as Track Plot

Long 663.GIN LONGITUDE (deg (+ve E))

656.JO1D	(E-5/S)
657.TECO NO	(ppb)
658.TECO NO2	(ppb)
659.TECO NOx	(ppb)
660.NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	(g m-3)
661.NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	(g m-3)
662.GIN LATITUDE	(deg (+ve N))
663.GIN LONGITUDE	(deg (+ve E))

Lat 662.GIN LATITUDE (deg (+ve N)) Red Line Del

P1 FL100

P1

P1

P1

End P1

DS2

DS3

DS4 small rift to LHS of us

DS5

End R1 start P2

Over POC now

Approx 11:58 LHS and 11:59 RHS pictures

P2 down across POC

P2 end, R2start

Start Run – called by Captain

R2

CT

CB

P3 end, R3 start 1000ft just below Cu CBs

Drizzle - clear above

CN going up now

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Flight B416 12:54:59
 Heading 237 deg Speed 0 knots Height 0.8kft Press 981mb
 Lat 20°6.0'S Long 78°12.0'W Wind 8 ms-1/ 159 deg
 Temp 19.04C Dewpoint 11.09C

T Td Plot From: 12:13 To: now -

Save plot parameters as T Td

515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs)

555.PSAP LOG ABS COEFF (m-1)
 556.PSAP TRANSMITTANCE (ratio)
 557.INS VERTICAL VELOCITY (m s-1 (+ve up))
 558.INS VELOCITY NORTH (m s-1 (+ve N))
 559.INS VELOCITY EAST (m s-1 (+ve E))
 560.INS ROLL (deg (+ve stbd))
 561.INS PITCH (deg (+ve up))
 562.INS HEADING (deg)

Y1 521.DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (deg C) Black Line Del
 Y2 529.DEW POINT (deg C) Red Line Del

Dec CCN conc=10/cc at 0.1%

End R3, start P4

Into drizzle

R4 int

R4 rec

Sonde 3	11:14:29	252	22.0kft	19.3S	73.3W													
sonde 4	11:22:24	253	22.0kft	19.5S	74.0W													
sonde 5	11:30:27	253	22.0kft	19.7S	74.7W													
Profile 2	12:03:01	241	12.8kft	20.1S	77.5W	12:10:30	242	4.9kft	20.3S	78.0W								
!	12:03:15	241	12.5kft	20.1S	77.6W													P2 late call
Run 2	12:10:30	242	4.9kft	20.3S	78.0W	12:31:08	049	5.0kft	19.7S	77.1W								
!	12:13:20	085	4.9kft	20.3S	78.0W													start run
!	12:14:07	071	4.9kft	20.2S	78.0W													ref S20 03.18 W 077 32.23
!	12:14:37	070	4.9kft	20.2S	77.9W													5000ft qnh 1016
!	12:15:06	068	5.0kft	20.2S	77.9W													rad 5100ft
nev	12:18:42	062	5.0kft	20.1S	77.7W													zero check
TW	12:18:51	060	5.0kft	20.1S	77.7W													zero check
Profile 3	12:31:09	049	5.0kft	19.7S	77.1W	12:35:21	241	0.91kft	19.6S	77.2W								
!	12:32:29	323	4.2kft	19.6S	77.1W													cloud tops 4300
!	12:33:33	327	2.9kft	19.6S	77.1W													cloud base 3000
Run 3	12:35:21	241	0.91kft	19.6S	77.2W	12:55:29	237	0.86kft	20.2S	78.3W								
!	12:36:14	242	0.93kft	19.6S	77.3W													qnh 1019
psap	12:38:10	242	0.81kft	19.7S	77.4W													flow off - drizzle
jw	12:40:14	230	0.87kft	19.7S	77.5W													zero
heimann	12:41:19	234	0.91kft	19.7S	77.5W													cal09
!	12:50:36	240	0.83kft	20.0S	78.0W													1246 sudden jump of 5C in thermometer readings
!	12:51:23	240	0.86kft	20.0S	78.1W													1061 radar
Profile 4	12:55:40	252	0.89kft	20.2S	78.3W	12:57:59	047	2.9kft	20.1S	78.3W								
Run 4	12:57:59	047	2.9kft	20.1S	78.3W													
R4	12:58:42	049	3.1kft	20.0S	78.3W													interrupted climbing
R4	12:59:49	051	3.8kft	20.0S	78.2W													resumed
!	13:00:07	055	3.8kft	20.0S	78.2W													cvi reports no TAS

Just in tops here - little gaps now and again

End Run

Start Saw tooth

CT

R5 T1

R5 CT 4500 (1019mB)

R5 B1 1000ft

CB Cu R5

R5 Sc CB

R5 CT

R5 T2

CT

Bumpy here !

Main CB

Cu CB

R5 B2

R5 CT

CT

R5 T3

R5 CT

R5 CT

R5 CB

R5 end

P6 start

P6 CB

P6 CT

End P6 start R6 FL230

DS6

Profile 3	12:31:09	049	5.0kft	19.7S	77.1W	12:35:21	241	0.91kft	19.6S	77.2W	
!	12:32:29	323	4.2kft	19.6S	77.1W						cloud tops 4300
!	12:33:33	327	2.9kft	19.6S	77.1W						cloud base 3000
Run 3	12:35:21	241	0.91kft	19.6S	77.2W	12:55:29	237	0.86kft	20.2S	78.3W	
!	12:36:14	242	0.93kft	19.6S	77.3W						qnh 1019
psap	12:38:10	242	0.81kft	19.7S	77.4W						flow off - drizzle
jw	12:40:14	230	0.87kft	19.7S	77.5W						zero
heimann	12:41:19	234	0.91kft	19.7S	77.5W						cal09
!	12:50:36	240	0.83kft	20.0S	78.0W						1246 sudden jump of 5C in thermometer readings
!	12:51:23	240	0.86kft	20.0S	78.1W						1061 radar
Profile 4	12:55:40	252	0.89kft	20.2S	78.3W	12:57:59	047	2.9kft	20.1S	78.3W	
Run 4	12:57:59	047	2.9kft	20.1S	78.3W	13:20:04	053	3.7kft	19.2S	77.3W	
R4	12:58:42	049	3.1kft	20.0S	78.3W						interrupted climbing
R4	12:59:49	051	3.8kft	20.0S	78.2W						resumed
!	13:00:07	055	3.8kft	20.0S	78.2W						cvi reports no TAS
!	13:05:52	051	3.8kft	19.8S	78.0W						port aft dlu reset after lock up
Profile 5	13:21:05	310	3.7kft	19.1S	77.3W	13:22:21	247	4.8kft	19.1S	77.4W	
Run 4	13:22:21	247	4.8kft	19.1S	77.4W	13:42:25	234	2.6kft	19.6S	78.6W	
!	13:22:59	247	4.3kft	19.2S	77.4W						error line above R5
!	13:26:11	245	0.89kft	19.2S	77.6W						sawtooth reversal V -> ^
!	13:30:54	245	4.9kft	19.3S	77.9W						sawtooth reversal ^ -> V
!	13:35:27	247	0.86kft	19.4S	78.2W						sawtooth reversal V -> ^
!	13:40:26	243	4.8kft	19.5S	78.5W						sawtooth reversal ^ => V
!	13:43:25	084	2.0kft	19.6S	78.6W						manouvre
Profile 6	13:44:22	083	0.87kft	19.6S	78.5W	14:07:42	088	23.0kft	19.4S	76.8W	
Run 6	14:07:43	088	23.0kft	19.4S	76.8W						
Sonde6	14:07:52	090	23.0kft	19.4S	76.8W						

Crossing/crossed boundary maritime/coastal

DS7

P6 Alan's "Ci layer"

Previous P3 down to just above POC

DS8

P6

P3

DS9

Flight B416 14:36:08
Heading 79 deg Speed 309 knots Height 23.0kft Press 408mb
Lat 19°6.0'S Long 74°12.0'W Wind 3 ms-1/ 342 deg
Temp -16.92C Dewpoint -33.41C
From 13:44:00 to now

Current values
PRESSURE HEIGHT 23.06 Kft All
OZONE MIXING RATIO 19.98 ppb

Flight B416 14:37:23
Heading 86 deg Speed 309 knots Height 23.0kft Press 408mb
Lat 19°0.0'S Long 74°6.0'W Wind 2 ms-1/ 353 deg
Temp -17.03C Dewpoint -31.2C
From 13:44:00 to now

Current values
PRESSURE HEIGHT 23.08 Kft All
CO MIXING RATIO 52.21 ppb

Flight B416 14:38:26
Heading 88 deg Speed 312 knots Height 23.0kft Press 409mb
Lat 19°0.0'S Long 74°0.0'W Wind 2 ms-1/ 345 deg
Temp -16.87C Dewpoint -31.0C
From 13:44:00 to now

Current values
PRESSURE HEIGHT 23.01 Kft All
TECO SO2 -2.26 ppb
TECO NOx -0.61 ppb

Flight B416 14:36:08
Heading 79 deg Speed 309 knots Height 23.0kft Press 408mb
Lat 19°5.0'S Long 74°12.0'W Wind 3 ms-1/ 342 deg
Temp -16.92C Dewpoint -33.41C
From 13:44:00 to now

Current values
PRESSURE HEIGHT 23.06 Kft All
OZONE MIXING RATIO 19.98 ppb

DS10 late!

DS11

psap	12:38:10	242	0.81kft	19.7S	77.4W						flow off - drizzle
jw	12:40:14	230	0.87kft	19.7S	77.5W						zero
heimann	12:41:19	234	0.91kft	19.7S	77.5W						cal09
!	12:50:36	240	0.83kft	20.0S	78.0W						1246 sudden jump of 5C in thermometer readings
!	12:51:23	240	0.86kft	20.0S	78.1W						1061 radar
Profile 4	12:55:40	252	0.89kft	20.2S	78.3W	12:57:59	047	2.9kft	20.1S	78.3W	
Run 4	12:57:59	047	2.9kft	20.1S	78.3W	13:20:04	053	3.7kft	19.2S	77.3W	
R4	12:58:42	049	3.1kft	20.0S	78.3W						interrupted climbing
R4	12:59:49	051	3.8kft	20.0S	78.2W						resumed
!	13:00:07	055	3.8kft	20.0S	78.2W						cvi reports no TAS
!	13:05:52	051	3.8kft	19.8S	78.0W						port aft dlu reset after lock up
Profile 5	13:21:05	310	3.7kft	19.1S	77.3W	13:22:21	247	4.8kft	19.1S	77.4W	
Run 4	13:22:21	247	4.8kft	19.1S	77.4W	13:42:25	234	2.6kft	19.6S	78.6W	
!	13:22:59	247	4.3kft	19.2S	77.4W						error line above R5
!	13:26:11	245	0.89kft	19.2S	77.6W						sawtooth reversal V -> ^
!	13:30:54	245	4.9kft	19.3S	77.9W						sawtooth reversal ^ -> V
!	13:35:27	247	0.86kft	19.4S	78.2W						sawtooth reversal V -> ^
!	13:40:26	243	4.8kft	19.5S	78.5W						sawtooth reversal ^ => V
!	13:43:25	084	2.0kft	19.6S	78.6W						manouvre
Profile 6	13:44:22	083	0.87kft	19.6S	78.5W	14:07:42	088	23.0kft	19.4S	76.8W	
Run 6	14:07:43	088	23.0kft	19.4S	76.8W						
Sonde6	14:07:52	090	23.0kft	19.4S	76.8W						
Sonde 7	14:15:43	087	23.0kft	19.3S	76.1W						
Sonde 8	14:23:44	085	23.0kft	19.2S	75.3W						
Sonde 9	14:31:44	081	23.0kft	19.1S	74.6W						
Sonde 10	14:41:15	078	23.1kft	19.1S	73.8W						
Sonde 11	14:48:06	087	22.9kft	19.0S	73.1W						

New plot, same times

Flight B416 14:55:54
Heading 81 deg Speed 316 knots Height 23.0kft Press 409mb
Lat 18°54.0'S Long 72°18.0'W Wind 2 ms-1/ 260 deg
Temp -16.96C Dewpoint -28.78C
From 13:44:00 to now

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 53754 secs All sc
 — EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP 333.86 K sc

New plot, same times

Flight B416 14:56:26
Heading 80 deg Speed 317 knots Height 23.0kft Press 409mb
Lat 18°54.0'S Long 72°18.0'W Wind 2 ms-1/ 261 deg
Temp -16.98C Dewpoint -28.11C
From 13:44:00 to now

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 53784 secs All sc
 — EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP 333.99 K sc

End R6 start P7

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Flight B416 15:12:14
Heading 83 deg Speed 243 knots Height 10.0kft Press 694mb
Lat 18°36.0'S Long 71°0.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 353 deg
Temp 12.76C Dewpoint -23.93C

T Td Plot From: 10:30 To: now -

- xy plot
- yx plot
- Tephigram
- Hodograph
- Track Plot
- Text
- LWC
- NOx SO2
- CO
- T Td**
- neph alt
- LWC alt
- T Td alt
- NOx alt
- CN
- NOx SO2 long
- T Td long
- vis lower
- O3 alt
- CO alt
- SO2 NOx alt
- Hum alt
- Hum
- O3
- Theta
- Neph
- Alt

plot parameters as T Td

GHT (secs)

- AIR TEMP (K)
- AIR TEMP (deg C)
- POTENTIAL TEMP (K)
- WIND (Nunits)
- TEMPERATURE (K)
- (kg m-3)
- (deg C)

Black Line Del
Red Line Del

Y1 521.D
Y2 529.D

Terminal
Shortcut to CD Drive
Mission ScilaptopSys...

Mission Scientist's Log

Miss. Sci.
2

Flight No B. 416 Date 7/11/08 Name Phil Brown Page 1 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
103146					1/2 roll ARI v. hazy below cloud.
103567		2500			cloud base.
—		3800			tops.
					Datum 208.03.18" S
					77 32.23 W
121320		¹⁰¹³ 5000	068		Run 2 5120 rad alt.
—					over cloud. some Cu pestrations around on the left.
1223					
123109					End run, profile.
—		4200			cloud tops
					v. triangular huc-profile
1243		1000			coming up to gap.
					Drizzle peaks only ~ 100' above
—			236		140/11 ms ⁻¹
1246					Temperature jump
1254					CCN dropping off.
		1000			End F3 just approaching a clear area.
		3900			
130730					CDP 20 35µm 500-800' on 2DC.
—					v. different droplets to what we've seen before.
130430	ish				RVSM reset.
—					big huc peak at 1311ish
1315					CDP drop sizes smaller and 2DC drizzle much lower.

9

0

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...416 Date 7/11/68 Name K.W. BOWER Page 1 of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
7:13:01-17	101h	KWB turn			Engine start, 4-1
7:24:53					Power change over
7:26:45					Taxing
7:32:09					Rolling
7:32:39	KWB				T/O - Overcast 8/8 - grey
10:32:20	T/O & P1 start				Proble Start (P1 1016) (140ft on ground!)
					CB 2500 (1013 p settings)
					CT 3900
10:42:00	7:42:21 KWB				(time check)
					Car dead OK, 2DS rock OK.
10:58:23	P1 end/R	FL220	251	18°54'/72°0'	-13.58°/-32.08 427mb 9m/s/207°
10:58:31	DS1	FL220	251	18°54'/72°0'	-13.61/-31.59°C 428mb 9m/s/211°
					Comms - I/nd to Vocals Calibrated ✓
					X dat - imminent - should get a packet
					few bits of Ci to LMS - but KWS - OK ahead
					720 mb - wet band - drops at 10°C at
				MS13	870 mb RH drops to 50% - drops to @
					750 mbar
11:06:24	DS 2	FL220	258	19°6'/72°36'	-13.75/-32.94°C 427mb 7m/s/219°
11:08:46					but some not showing any winds yet
					across 75 W - no sign of riffs yet
11:14:27	DS 3	FL220	252	19°18'/75°12'	-13.85/-30.88 427mb 6m/s/231°
					Big nice oscillations - descending - slow w
					Some riffs (small) coming up at this time

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.416 Date 7/11/09 Name K.N. Bower Page 2 of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Vertical winds - MS _{ci} 3 ⇒ going into
11:19:00					{ region slow subsiding small rift to the - few bumps here !! LHS of us here ←
11:22:22	D54	FL220	253	19°30'/75°54'	last some grad too -13.9°/28.3° Smts/245°
11:26:00					MS _{ci} 3 Dry pod T- still dropping (⊖) ⊖ _{av} stabilised.
					"Large" rift feature ahead (12:03)
11:30:25	D55	FL220	252	19°42'/74°42'	-13.72°/-34.38° 428mb Smts/256° FSSP 450 on PI through cloud GOES-10 VIS 10:58 UTC ⇒ [20S 77.5W]
11:36:30					MS _{ci} 3- Satellite picture agrees with observations Cooled air mass qv ↓ dropped significantly ⊖ also ↓ ⊖ _e
					Vertical velocities lifted off- processes are visible (convergence - central region) - sea area up/flat
11:54:51	P4E/P2	FL220	274	20°/76°54'	-14.31°/26.11° 429mb 7mb/259° last some - huge drop in dew pt - really in oceanic air mass now.
					← heading for X feature - fly along → ? or ?
					nice inversion in T & q _v - dry layer SSOmb coming down - Will go across POC
12:01:26	P2	14.3kt	274	20°/77°24'	586mb 4.41°C/-34.9°C Rmb/259° will do P ₁ run across POC - eos on sec it now.

picture taken at this

Neb Flight Man PC - Flight Folder - B416
latest Sat Pic

[20S, 77.5] new Zulu from sat pic

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 416 Date 7/11/08 Name K N Bower Page 3 of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts	
					Reduced legs to 20mins to get run in 90mins avail	
					MSi3 series T unavergans 50mh sep	
					- region of subsidence?	
					Core Chem - highest O ₃ so far - 55 ppb in legs here...	
				Coastal AF ⇒ (205 03.15' W, 077° 32.23') (Z)		
5000ft	12:10:28	Plend / R2 4.9kft	242	20°12'/78°0'	turning for 4 cross POC runs + turns etc / above Radar alt of 4.9kft ≈ 5000ft } below in 14.1°/-12.21°C 845mb 11m/s/140° } saw track	
	12:13:08	Run 2 start (captain)	5000ft	90°	20°12'/78°0'	(1016 mb. settings) 844mb 14.2°/-15.16°C 10m/s/140° CON 30/200 @ 0.1% (ie SE wind here) PCASR - rem ch 1 N=240 (ch 1 using ch 2 conc to make up spectrum)
	12:14:06	R2	4.9kft	58°	20°6'/77°30'	14.79°/-21.69°C 7m/s/109° 846mb MSi3 p
	12:19:06	R2	At 4.9kft	58°	20°6'/77°30'	POC edge on LHS of us now - need to drift NW on return leg - drift with wind O ₃ / cm ³ CAS SO ₄ - slightly ↑ 0.2 μg/l ³ Slight dec 25 → 15/200 → 240 CON/CON PCASR 250 → 125 over region
	12:31:09	R2 end / P3	4.9kft	49	19°42'/77°	15.87°/29.55° 843mb 3m/s/81° MSi3 - end run pol ¹ T ± 2°C and O ₃ by mixing ratio → 0.5 g/kg ?? Radar Alt sum...
	10:32:29	P3	4.1kft	321	19°36'/77°	CT - 4300ft 5.45°/-6.95°C 868mb 9/140°
	10:33:29	P3	3.0kft	326	19°30'/77°6'	CS → 3000ft 7.17°/8.36°C 906mb 8m/s/140°

MSi3 6000ft for Saw track ?? maybe.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 416 Date 7/11/08 Name K. N. BOWEN Page 4 of 8

1000H

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12:35:21	P3en/13	0.9kft	241	19°30'/77°12'	980ml 13.5°/8.92C 9mls/157° (drift ↘) (1019 mb sat) No Inc in CCN 50/230 few Cu - 12-1300ft CB. MS: 3 - Turb very clean for waves. ZDS - little drizzle - ~ 250 µm Circ Cloud 500 µm Qv = 0.7 - 0.9 g/kg
12:39:00	R3				drizzle again
12:40:00	R3				dry - brights start ahead here.
12:40:57	R3				drizzle - v light Hole in cloud ahead - slightly RMS
12:42:17	R3	0.9kft	237	19°42'/77°30'	drizzle but clear above us - blue across?
12:44:00					CCN - just decreases to 150 cm ³ CCN going down too Mo - sudden message on X chat - not getting No change measure of O ₃ , CO, water level slight ↓ CO. total aucts ↑ (N=30)
[1ENB @ 12:46 Overall speed = 210 kts]					M3 - pitch T ↑ 6° @ 12:46 ????
[1 true speed → 0 kts.]					M2 - doesn't believe - T jumped 5° - uncalibrated but we didn't change much (M3) same time as CCN increased

40-50 CCN. } from 5 12:46
NB was down out to } sharp.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.416 Date 7/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 5 of 8

1000'
1000'
3000'
3000'
3900'

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					12:46: W 0 → 3 m/s - drizzle
					remember that altit - used in calc of
					limb radii values etc.
				 check it out..
12:54.59	R3	0.8kft	237	20°6'/76°12'	CCN ↓ to 10 as CN 250-200
12:55:31	R3/R4	0.8kft	237	20°6'/76°15'	962mb 18.99°/10.72°C 10m/s/153°
12:57.59	R1/R4	2.9kft			3000ft - just vis Cir bases here
12:58.28	R4mt	2.9kft	51	20°/76°12'	A 3900ft to get into main Sc deck. 910m
12:59.50	R4mt	3.5kft	51	14°54'/76°12'	ZDS is seen 300 as CAS, φ=15µm 880mb 250 15µm.
					7AS 220kts -
13:02.50					ZDS: LWC - ↑
					In gap
					RVS 1AS → 0 -
					NO CCN - here.
					lot of drizzle drops here.
					CDC - still dual peaks - molecular
					CDP - N ↓ 20 φ 35 !!!
					ZDC - 1000 / 2 @ 150µm
					FSSM - N ≈ 30 φ 28µm
					gradual drop in CDP ≈ 100 φ 20
					FSSM - 150 φ 18
					CAS gradual ↑ drop size - structured.
					in total No's.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....416 Date7/11/08..... NameK.N. ZOWER..... Page6..... of8.....

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					CAS N ↑ climb 150 → 900
					(hold 1
					QFF Φ same - high 30-32
					dropping down again now.
					Φ stayed same
13:17.6h					CAS Φ been decreasing - N ↑ and ↓
13:21.10	RS ↓	at 3.7ht	310	19.1/77.3	1 st Climb Clear CT and then start saw back (from above) CT)
13:22.21	RS ↑				Start
13:22.04	RS ↑	4.4ht	249	19°6'/77°18'	CT 4500ft 850mb 15.34/3.08 Snds/130°
13:22.25	RS ↑	5000	247	19°6'/77°16'	15.89/-17.66°C 848mb (strong inversion) 4m/s/146°
13:22.58	RS ↓	4.3ht	247	19°6'/77°24'	CT 4500ft again 866mb 10.65/-25.35° 8/146°
					(pressure setting 10Kmb)
13:25.08	RS ↓	1.9ht	240	19°12'/77°30'	CB - (some bin alter) 943mb 10.48/9.3°C
13:26.11	RS B1	0.8ht	245	19°12'/77°30'	981mb 13.89°C/9.33°C 10m/s/146°
13:27.49	RS ↑	2.0ht	245	19°12'/77°36'	CB Cu 2000ft ish 10.33/9.18°C 939mb 8/146°
13:28.51	RS ↑	3.0ht	246	19°12'/77°42'	CB Sc 3000ft ish 7.85/8.75°C 904mb 8/152°
13:30.05	RS ↑	4.2ht	249	19°18'/77°48'	CT 4500ft 4.61/8.16°C 866mb 8m/s/160°
13:30.51	RS ↑	4.8ht	246	19°18'/77°48'	5000ft 16.36/-20.35° 846mb 4m/s/146°
					2DS saw large - drops as in fact
13:31.40	RS ↓	4.3ht	243	19°18'/77°51'	CT again 4500ft 865mb 7.23/9.27°C 8m/s/137°
					V des air above inversion - strong cut line
13:32.41	RS ↓	3.5ht			Bumpy.
13:32.04	RS ↓	3.0ht	245	19°18'/78°	CB near deck here 906mb 7.5/7.8°C 11m/s/146°
13:34.12	RS ↓	1.9ht	247	19°18'/78°	CB Cu = 2000' 943mb 10.4/10.1°C 10m/s/141°
13:36.24	RS B2	0.9ht	247	19°24'/78°6'	1000ft 980mb 13.62/9.96°C 10m/s/136

↙

1000ft

5000ft

↙

13:20:00 R4and 3.7ht 53 19°6'/77°12' 884mb 6.18°/8.34°C 8m/s/130°

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 416

Date 7/11/08

Name K. N. Bower

Page 7 of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13:37:23	RS ↑	2.2kt	242	19°24'/76°12'	933mb 9.84°/9.03°C 12ms/150° CB.
13:39:21	RS ↑	4.1kt	247	19°24'/76°24'	CT 869mb 5.09°/7.24° 10ms/149°
13:40:09	RST3	4.7kt	244	19°30'/76°24'	850mb 14.24°/20.45°C 8ms/Kel° strong inv
13:41:13	RS ↑	4.0kt	245	19°30'/76°30'	CT, 875mb / 13:42:06 CB 2.9hft. 909mb
13:42:16	RS end	2.7kt	245	19°30'/76°30'	916mb 8.54°/8.97°C 10ms/136°
					AMS - another very dry patch
					- no oscillations
					- no enhanced air.
13:44:20	P6 start	0.8kt	84	19°30'/76°30'	descended below P6 at 1000ft 13.63°/11.66° 8ms/124° 981mb
13:47:11	P6 1	3.2kt	78	19°30'/76°18'	CB det 899mb 7.12°/7.63°C 10ms/124°
13:48:09	P6 ↑	4.2kt	88	19°30'/76°12'	CT (4200 Certain)
					866mb 4.61°/7.18° 11ms/113°
					Sket w' collection eff. 0.5 - nothing > 1μm ²
					(maybe ↓ in POC-lets!) Sket
					measured 60m/s with wind in 1/2 hrs >
					than windspeed ⇒
					POC to air left - Schlieren Picture
					regress.
					Very Very stable patch - M3
14:07:40	P6e/P6	P2230	87	19°18'/76°48'	410mb -17.06°/-36.08° 7ms/345°
14:07:44	DS6	P2230	89	19°18'/76°42'	409mb -17.03°/-36.65° 7ms/345°

(56mm to top descent P7 ⇒ Arica 15-25ish)

13:40:56 RS ↑ 4.2kt 243 19°30'/76°30' 866mb CT 8.41°/-17.59°C 11ms/150°

unsent
*

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 416 Date 7/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 8 of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					⊖ changed 14.10
					⊖w changed / change
14:14:00	R6				q _v ↑ from 0.4 → shift ↑ also - on sea NW-SE "rifts"
14:14:23	R6	FL230	77	19°12'/76°6'] in dual structure [cross Ma/Cast Borders 409mb -16.79°/-34.48° 7m/s/353°
14:15:41	DS7	FL230	86	19°12'/76°0'	
					⊖ - sched - at 14.00
					q _v = 0.4 → 0.65 - related in ⊖w
					heights constant.
					W ⇒ period ascent - ??
					Clearly in ascent - sun now.
14:23:42	DS8	FL230	85	19°6'/75°18'	q _v settled down: 0.4 → 0.7 g/hk now
					⊖w increased - little change in ⊖
14:31:42	DS9	FL230	81	19°6'/74°30'	409mb -16.8°/-30.76° 4m/s/354°
14:41:12	DS10	FL230	77	19°0'/73°42'	407mb -17.2/-30.34 2m/s/323°
					W side - 4-5mins - definite dry field stream
					at: 14.31 - 14.37
14:47:50	DS11	FL230	88	18°54'/75°6'	409mb -17.04°/-30.13°C 1m/s/301°
					W edge of N Jet - Head comes down
					cont - just above it
14:59:20	R6/P7	FL230	74°	18°48'/72°0'	410mb -16.84°/-28.39°C 2m/s/264°
15:22:12h (ONB)	P7	4500'			(T (1017 mb setting)
15:23:29	P7	2940'			CB
15:27:49	Land.				Landing at Ania.

Fillies OK ✓

Nerthe 1300 Nerth ✓

Down S. 1 in late winds Slick Dim Grad.

OVI ✓

AMS ✓

Core Chem ✓ for on ~~to~~ O₃

CO

NO_x

SO₂

Cloud Phys - PCASP₂

still has a leak

changed a few things yesterday - removed ch1 (del reg run)

put down 2 voltages to get balance

Comes still too high - quadrature all else OK

AGUES

MANB

SWS -

probos indirectly - in profile - red OIC

low STMS OIC - sure it kin. issue

CEN - 1 channel

VACE - Not much at the - water here

ZDS

CAPS

Headset B missing - not signed for

Clipboard - issues

Photo Album

Start left on board for search

12:50 - Temp 5°

OVI TAS - not getting

Comments → TAS Auto error - reset - arrange reset of bit

- start TAS - demand 1305 1250-1305

OK in Workshop date - with number given on our work

- want have history of things not

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/11/07 19:30

Author of report: Keith Bower

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/11/09 20:02

Remaining flight hours: 20

General Comments:

After POC flight 3 (B416) on 7/11/2008

INSTRUMENTS/SYSTEMS STATUS

 = up;
 = provisional;
 = down ;
 = no report

Meteorology/Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	core data suffered problem at 12:50 - poss related to IAS issue - reset 13:50. Data using online IAS may have error for this period
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	11 sondes launched - 1 had late wind data.

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:	
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:	
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:	
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:	problems initially in profile - rest OK
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment:	lower SHIMS ok
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:	

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:	leak from cabin detected and fixed - Ozone data looks better/believable
17.	NOx	Comment:	
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:	
19.	SO2 (TECO 43C)	Comment:	
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment:	not carried in VOCALS
21.	CH4/CO2 (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:	
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment:	not operated
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:	

24. **CH4/N2O (1C-TDLAS)** Comment:

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	believed to still have leak - Ch2 counts substituted for Ch1 counts to generate spectrum/total concs, but concs still too high
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	not fitted
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	needs alignment
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	only 1 channel working
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	

39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	
41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	
42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment:	
43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:	
44.	CAPS	Comment:	
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment:	not fitted
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment:	not fitted
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:	
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:	
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:	

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:	
51.	SATCOM H	Comment:	
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:	

[prev](#) | [next](#)

 [Back to VOCALS Field Catalog](#) | [edit](#) | [delete](#)

comments : [gstoss at ucar.edu](#)

Chemistry Log

Date: 7/11/08 Flight: B416 Operator: KT

Preflight CO, O₃, NO_x, SO₂ operated

No. ? or x	Location	Action	Comments
Gases			
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO ₂ /Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO ₂ /Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure
Flows			
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 0.7 LPM on both channels
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO _x sample flow	~ 1 LPM
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO _x Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO cell pressure	~ 7.5 bar
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO Pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar
Zeros			
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO _x zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO zero	Left for approx 10 min
Other			
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)
TDLAS			
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	230V	230V power breakers on
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Laptop	On and software working
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Data	Being saved to correct directories
<i>Driers (both) changed post B415, pre B416</i>			
Post Flight			
Switch off			
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO	Switch off instrument
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Ozone	Switch off monitor
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO _x	Switch off monitor
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pumps	Switch off all pumps
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP
Gases (note pressures)			
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO ₂ /Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi
If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling			
Driers			
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Small drier	Change if spent
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Large drier	Change if spent
TDLAS			
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Data transfer	To memory stick
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Laptop	Shut down
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on
Log			
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC

Chemistry Log

In flight

B416

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.

During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
10:29	Taxi	92.26	303.48	288 28183	40.56	7.54
Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)

CO 'Cal'

Flight level	Zero Start	Zero End Conc	Counts (Hz)	Span Start	Span End	Conc. Range	Counts range	Sensitivity	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	Lamp Temp	O3 Intensities CELL B
FL220	11:01:30	-13 to -6	27585	11:02:40	11:03:30	494 to 513	73724	60	33387	7.46	40.5	12.3558	
FL220	11:07	O ₃ - 10.8	- 12.1										
	11:08	Inlet dis connected to sample Cabin air - should see pressure spike									P=652 mmHg		A=0.678
		Cabin O ₃ - 0.8ish											B=0.696
	11:12	Inlet reattached									P=904 mmHg		A=0.822
													B=0.853
	11:28	-8	27300	11:47		500	74700				7.45	40.50	114616
		cap off		11:49									
FL049	12:13	-7	27400			504	74700				7.50	40.50	111625
FL039	13:00	-8	27400			508	75200				7.54	39.65	111860
FL230	14:16	-13 to -5	27128	14:18		508	75091				7.37	39.87	112204
FL230	14:50	-13 to -9	26757	14:55		508	73967				7.33	40.51	113080

O₃ p = 650
 O₃ p = 909
 O₃ p = 747
 O₃ p = 750
 O₃ p = 646
 O₃ p = 645.5

In flight comments

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 416

Date: 08:30:00 **Operator: MAP** **DRS Time: +0** **DAU1 Time: +0** **DAU2 Time: +0** **DAU3 Time: +0** **Aux1 Time: +0** **Aux2 Time: +0** **Page 1 of 4**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
08:40:00																40.6 Microns into Manchester FSSP	
08:51:00																30.1 Microns into Manchester FSSP	
08:55:15																17.4 Microns into Manchester FSSP	
08:59:00																14.1 Microns into Manchester FSSP	
09:03:00																9.6 Microns into Manchester FSSP	
09:07:00																5.6 Microns into Manchester FSSP	
10:35:17	1400	0.08	3			5	275	480	10				250	15	0.4	1	FL020
10:36:45	2100	0.20	147			45	275	220	18				200	20	0.8	1	FL030
10:37:47	770	0.07															FL040
10:38:44	400	0.07	197														FL050
10:40:02	600	0.07															FL060
10:40:57	675	0.08															FL070
10:42:08	170	0.07															FL080
10:43:25	60	0.07															FL090
10:44:37																	FL100
10:46:08	100	0.07															FL110
10:46:55	210	0.07															FL120
10:47:58	80	0.08															FL130
10:48:49	35	0.08															FL140
10:50:05	30	0.07															FL150
10:51:16	40	0.07															FL160
10:52:36	25	0.07															FL170
10:53:53	10	0.07															FL180
10:55:05	15	0.07															FL190
10:56:09	10	0.07															FL200
10:57:18	10	0.07															FL210
10:58:28																	End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1 @ FL220
10:59:00	10	0.07															
11:05:00	10	0.07															
11:10:00	5	0.07															
11:15:00	5	0.07	198														
11:20:00	10	0.07															
11:25:00	10	0.07															
11:30:00	5	0.07															
11:35:00	10	0.07															
11:40:00	5	0.07															
11:45:00	7	0.07	207														
11:50:00	7	0.07															
11:54:56	8	0.07															Start Profile 2 from FL220
11:55:41	20	0.06															FL210
11:56:30	20	0.07															FL200
11:57:17	20	0.06															FL190
11:58:07	20	0.07															FL180

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 416

Date: 08:30:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:59:02	20	0.07														FL170	
11:59:57	40	0.07														FL160	
12:00:50	30	0.06														FL150	
12:01:52	35	0.07														FL140	
12:02:48	38	0.07														FL130	
12:03:43	36	0.07														FL120	
12:04:30	30	0.07														FL110	
12:05:30	25	0.07														FL100	
12:06:33	120	0.07														FL090	
12:07:28	160	0.07														FL080	
12:08:26	260	0.07														FL070	
12:09:24	250	0.08														FL060	
12:10:48	230	0.07														End of Profile @ 5000'	
12:13:12																Start Run 2 @ 5000'	
12:14:00	250	0.07															
12:16:00	230	0.07															
12:18:00	220	0.07															
12:20:00	150	0.07															
12:22:00	175	0.07															
12:24:00	150	0.07															
12:26:00	170	0.07															
12:28:00	130	0.07															
12:30:00	125	0.07															
12:31:19																End of Run 2 & Start Profile 3	
12:32:37	650	0.21	244			7	200	180	20			0.7	120	20	0.5	1	FL040
12:33:45	390	0.07	290			1	200									1	FL030
12:34:26	450	0.07															FL020
12:35:20																	End of Profile 3 & Start Run 3 @ 1000'
12:36:00	445	0.07															
12:38:00	500	0.07				1	500									1	
12:40:00	350	0.07															
12:42:00	370	0.07				2											
12:44:00	140	0.07															
12:46:00	360	0.07															
12:48:00	260	0.07															
12:50:00	310	0.07	294														
12:52:00	310	0.07															
12:54:00	150	0.07															
12:55:26																	End of Run & Start Profile 4
12:57:13	200	0.07				10	200										FL020
12:59:50																	End of Profile & start Run 4 @ 3900'
13:00:00	550	0.20	357			4	100	155	17			0.25	120	19	0.2	12	
13:02:00	600	0.22	466			60	200	155	17			0.35	100	21	0.4	1	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 416

Date: 08:30:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
13:04:00	1100	0.21	581			200	275	70	20			0.5	60	22	0.2	1	
13:06:00	210	0.23	639			260	225	35	20			0.25	20	30	0.2	1	
13:10:00	800	0.24	690			440	175	50	30			0.3	40	30	0.4	1	
13:12:00	830	0.23	812			400	225	50	28			0.3	80	25	0.4	1	
13:14:00	1000	0.23	895			60	150	100	22			0.6	100	25	1.0	1	
13:16:00	1100	0.25	1038			70	225	70	22			0.4	80	22	0.6	1	
13:18:00	1400	0.23	1191			30	225	140	21			0.5	100	22	0.6	1	
13:20:05																	End of Run
13:21:05																	Start Run 5
13:21:41	150	0.07	1422														FL040
13:22:20	150	0.07															FL050
13:23:17	740	0.22	1438			16	225	150	22			1.0	100	25	0.6	1	FL040
13:24:22	160	0.12	1523			4	350										FL030
13:25:09	330	0.07	1524														FL020
13:26:08	395	0.07															FL010
13:27:50	292	0.07															FL020
13:28:55	300	0.09	1526			100	325	100	20			0.3	50	28	0.4	1	FL030
13:30:00	130	0.09	1566			600	175	50	30			1.0	50	30	0.8	1	FL040
13:31:03	140	0.07	1570														FL050
13:31:53	670	0.23	1589			300	200	75	28			0.7	50	24	0.3	1	FL040
13:33:10	100	0.07	1616			2											FL030
13:34:07	300	0.08															FL020
13:35:15	220	0.07															FL010
13:37:03	250	0.07	1617														FL020
13:38:11	250	0.07				8	200										FL030
13:39:20	700	0.23	1674			40	175	140	20			0.7	100	22	0.6		FL040
13:40:24	150	0.07															FL050
13:41:07	700	0.23	1701			40	200	100	20			0.4	60	20	0.3	1	FL040
13:42:29	300	0.07	1746														End of Run @ FL030
13:44:23	330	0.07															Start Profile 6 from 1000'
13:45:45	310	0.07	1745														FL020
13:46:57	320	0.07	1747														FL030
13:47:52	600	0.23	1803			500	150	150	30			0.8	70	30	0.6	1	FL040
13:49:29	155	0.07	1814														FL050
13:50:36	80	0.07															FL060
13:51:36	130	0.07															FL070
13:52:44	130	0.07															FL080
13:53:53	80	0.07															FL090
13:54:46	20	0.07															FL100
13:55:49	20	0.07															FL110
13:56:45	20	0.07															FL120
13:57:49	25	0.07															FL130
13:58:50	20	0.07															FL140

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 416

Date: 08:30:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
13:59:55	15	0.06	1814													FL150	
14:00:58	20	0.07														FL160	
14:02:03	10	0.07														FL170	
14:02:48	10	0.06														FL180	
14:03:49	11	0.07														FL190	
14:04:33	5	0.07														FL200	
14:05:38	5	0.07														FL210	
14:06:33	5	0.07														FL220	
14:07:43	5	0.06														End of Profile & Start Run 6 @FL230	
14:08:00	10	0.07															
14:10:00	10	0.06															
14:15:00	8	0.06															
14:20:00	7	0.06															
14:25:00	10	0.07															
14:30:00	10	0.07															
14:35:00	7	0.07															
14:40:00	10	0.06	1815														
14:45:00	10	0.06															
14:50:00	8	0.06															
14:55:00	7	0.06															
14:59:24																End of Run & Start Profile 7 from FL230	
15:00:14	10	0.07														FL220	
15:01:04	15	0.07														FL210	
15:02:00	10	0.06														FL200	
15:02:48	10	0.07														FL190	
15:03:54	15	0.07														FL180	
15:04:51	15	0.07														FL170	
15:05:59	25	0.07														FL160	
15:07:12	50	0.07														FL150	
15:08:23	35	0.07														FL140	
15:09:36	40	0.07														FL130	
15:10:40	120	0.07														FL120	
15:11:20	180	0.07														FL110	
15:12:15	170	0.07														FL100	
15:13:14	65	0.07														FL090	
15:14:30	60	0.07														FL080	
15:16:22	620	0.08														FL070	
15:18:28	505	0.07														FL060	
	PCASP Conc based on CH1 counts being removed and replaced with Ch2 values																

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B416	Date	07/11/2008	Operator	KFT	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
105836	1	Launch	428.60 -13.50 22.26 211.20 9.30 1.00 -72.035000 -18.935600 6694.60
110726	1	Splashdown	1008.15 15.97 74.84 167.08 4.35 -11.48 -72.026737 -18.931363 -298.14
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.
110630	2	Launch	427.50 -13.80 22.38 221.60 7.40 0.80 -72.669400 -19.120200 6712.10
111516	2	Splashdown	1007.22 16.24 69.97 179.92 3.67 -11.55 -72.659449 -19.118400 -298.39
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first. Late winds.
111433	3	Launch	427.70 -13.80 23.46 232.50 6.70 0.80 -73.301900 -19.324200 6709.30
112322	3	Splashdown	1007.27 16.43 68.26 167.17 4.65 -11.76 -73.288409 -19.322500 -297.65
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.
112227	4	Launch	427.60 -13.90 27.75 244.40 5.70 0.40 -73.997300 -19.518000 6710.20
113125	4	Splashdown	1006.88 16.13 74.88 165.37 4.54 -11.43 -73.984086 -19.514798 -295.03
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.
113030	5	Launch	428.40 -13.70 16.14 257.00 5.90 0.30 -74.711300 -19.747700 6697.40
113914	5	Splashdown	1007.78 16.35 65.90 150.96 7.07 -12.69 -74.695714 -19.741790 -295.75
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.
140754	6	Launch	409.60 -17.10 16.02 345.20 7.30 0.30 -76.789300 -19.353700 7017.70
141701	6	Splashdown	1005.86 15.58 65.00 145.70 9.23 -10.32 -76.781846 -19.345695 -298.62
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.
141545	7	Launch	409.40 -16.80 20.04 354.00 7.40 0.60 -76.058500 -19.285600 7020.20
142454	7	Splashdown	1005.78 15.82 68.49 144.70 7.71 -10.67 -76.046854 -19.280340 -299.53
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.
142348	8	Launch	409.80 -16.80 26.56 351.10 5.20 0.40 -75.331500 -19.190700 7012.80
143251	8	Splashdown	1004.85 15.85 72.12 173.16 6.53 -11.06 -75.324649 -19.186918 -299.42
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.
143148	9	Launch	409.50 -16.80 28.95 352.60 4.80 0.30 -74.606700 -19.144400 7018.90
144048	9	Splashdown	1003.62 16.35 67.37 151.58 5.66 -9.35 -74.596640 -19.144290 -294.15
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.
144118	10	Launch	409.50 -17.00 30.57 320.70 1.90 0.50 -73.745500 -19.049400 7018.10
145030	10	Splashdown	1003.39 16.43 72.12 162.34 4.48 -10.48 -73.736539 -19.050649 -295.19
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.
144800	11	Launch	410.20 -16.90 30.90 294.80 1.70 0.50 -73.120400 -18.984600 7006.70
145710	11	Splashdown	1003.58 16.53 70.88 156.20 3.73 -7.50 -73.109976 -18.986437 -296.91
			Parachute repacked. Launched sensor end first.

size	#	charged	Flight/Date	Discharged	Comments
10	1	4/11	NOT USED	—	
1	2	KNSB			
10	3	4/11	B416	8/11/08	
1	4	KNSB	7/11/08	HC	
10	21	3/11	B416	8/11/08	
1	23	KNSB	7/11/08	HC	
10	7	S/11	NOT USED	—	
1	8	KNSB			
10	10	S/11	NOT USED	—	
1	69	KNSB			
10	33	S/11	NOT USED	—	
1	40	KNSB			

Filter #	Loc ^{IN}	T _{ON}	T _{OFF}	RUN	TOT F
21, 23	U	12:40	12:47	R3	430
3, 4	L	12:47	12:55	R3	543

1016

B416

~~Handwritten scribbles~~

15/25
 H-CVI

Flight:

B416

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B416

Date: 07/11/08

Instruments

Drosondes	11 dropped, 1 delayed winds Slickness of drop-person noted
CVI -	ok
Filters	ok
Neph	ok
PSAP	ok
WetNeph	ok
AMS	ok
Core Chem	ok
Cloud physics -	CO fix giving better numbers
ARIES -	PCASP channel 1 noisy otherwise scale error
MARSS -	ok
SWS -	ok
CCN -	ok, single channel only
VACC -	ok
2DS -	ok,
CAPS -	ok,
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

One ISDN connection for satpic

MPDS

Run for flight, connected but data rate low and IE would not connect to sites, Xchat unavailable
Isdn used to get satpic with no problem

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Issues

12:50 temperatures jumped 5C
13:00 CVI reported no TAS feed
fault traced to locked up port aft DLU
13:05 DLU reset – fault cleared.

Loss of IAS and, possibly, static pressure will propagate into all derived data

Can be recovered by;

1. reworking data using turbulence probe pitot and S9 static to generate IAS
2. assuming constant IAS to fill gap

CVI log

11/7/08 9:58:22 AM lyman returned on counterflow directed through
11/7/08 9:58:35 AM will have the lyman drying until after take off
11/7/08 10:02:58 AM counterflow off for a minute just to check any counts coming through on pcasp
11/7/08 10:05:50 AM aqll good, counterflow back on
11/7/08 10:40:08 AM counterflow off followong take off
11/7/08 10:41:17 AM counterflow off followong take off
11/7/08 10:43:19 AM re zero the lyman after the first sonde
11/7/08 10:53:03 AM drop off in pcasp concs up here
11/7/08 10:53:09 AM cpc climbing
11/7/08 10:53:26 AM cpc climbing
11/7/08 10:54:09 AM layers in aerosl structure, aboutt 300 above cloud, ab
11/7/08 10:55:23 AM careful with aerosol data on legs with sondes as banking into turns will affect the intake effeciency
11/7/08 10:59:39 AM zero lyman again
11/7/08 10:59:46 AM have altered dilution factor
11/7/08 11:03:38 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:04:05 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:04:08 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:04:12 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:04:54 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:04:58 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:07:34 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:07:37 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:14:10 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:22:29 AM no change in lyman values execpt for the noise around zero. back to sample from plenum
11/7/08 11:23:14 AM need to be able to get the graphical display in terms of time, maybe some way of stamping run times
11/7/08 11:28:04 AM need to be able to get the graphical display in terms of time, maybe some way of stamping run times
11/7/08 11:28:07 AM need to be able to get the graphical display in terms of time, maybe some way of stamping run times
11/7/08 11:28:11 AM need to be able to get the graphical display in terms of time, maybe some way of stamping run times
11/7/08 11:28:17 AM need to be able to get the graphical display in terms of time, maybe some way of stamping run times
11/7/08 11:31:55 AM test if any crap is in the system after the work
11/7/08 11:31:58 AM ams going to cvi
11/7/08 11:32:04 AM leave cvi in aerosol mode
11/7/08 11:36:45 AM into cvi mode at 2.4
11/7/08 11:37:07 AM cpc just saw a drop off in concentrations prior to switch over
11/7/08 11:37:18 AM was this the coastal boundary
11/7/08 11:37:33 AM spikes on CPC and Ly indicate the time of switch over
11/7/08 11:43:04 AM back into aerosol mode
11/7/08 11:43:18 AM no sign of contam from plenum works yesterday
11/7/08 11:52:27 AM reduce ly dilution factor from 0.7 to 0.1
11/7/08 11:54:50 AM profile descent
11/7/08 11:56:18 AM drop and increase in cpc counts over last few minutes from 400-300 and back
11/7/08 11:57:28 AM falling away from coast and increasing as we drop
11/7/08 11:57:40 AM over POC
11/7/08 11:59:29 AM super drop off in cpc
11/7/08 11:59:33 AM super drop off in cpc
11/7/08 11:59:37 AM super drop off in cpc
11/7/08 11:59:47 AM super drop off in cpc
11/7/08 11:59:59 AM super drop off in cpc
11/7/08 12:00:04 PM super drop off in cpc

11/7/08 12:00:07 PM super drop off in cpc
11/7/08 12:00:16 PM fall in lwc
11/7/08 12:02:27 PM fall in lwc
11/7/08 12:03:47 PM counterflow is OFF, lyman is sampling from PLENUM
11/7/08 12:08:36 PM pcasp seeing things now
11/7/08 12:10:16 PM pcasp seeing things now
11/7/08 12:11:02 PM turning for above cloud run
11/7/08 12:13:09 PM run now above cloud
11/7/08 12:15:09 PM run now above cloud
11/7/08 12:15:14 PM run now above cloud
11/7/08 12:15:18 PM run now above cloud
11/7/08 12:19:30 PM tio is over temp at this altitude, heated by the counterflow air
11/7/08 12:21:32 PM tio is over temp at this altitude, heated by the counterflow air
11/7/08 12:21:38 PM tio is over temp at this altitude, heated by the counterflow air
11/7/08 12:25:09 PM tio is over temp at this altitude, heated by the counterflow air
11/7/08 12:25:14 PM tio is over temp at this altitude, heated by the counterflow air
11/7/08 12:32:26 PM MS3 - drop off in moisture - comparable to lycwc
11/7/08 12:32:34 PM now profileling down through cloud
11/7/08 12:32:45 PM still in aerosol mode
11/7/08 12:32:53 PM silly counts now
11/7/08 12:33:24 PM out of cloud
11/7/08 12:33:30 PM out of cloud
11/7/08 12:33:35 PM out of cloud
11/7/08 12:34:44 PM white caps on waves
11/7/08 12:35:19 PM run under could started at 10337
11/7/08 12:36:38 PM under Cu base, bumpy
11/7/08 12:36:53 PM very clean temp inversion on last profile
11/7/08 12:37:07 PM very clean temp inversion on last profile
11/7/08 12:37:56 PM drizzle from cloud physics
11/7/08 12:38:11 PM large counts on cpc and pcasp - shattering?
11/7/08 12:39:51 PM large counts on cpc and pcasp - shattering?
11/7/08 12:39:56 PM large counts on cpc and pcasp - shattering?
11/7/08 12:41:02 PM drizzlen again - picked up in cpc counts
11/7/08 12:41:52 PM drizzlen again - picked up in cpc counts
11/7/08 12:42:02 PM drizzlen again - picked up in cpc counts
11/7/08 12:42:30 PM drizzlen again - picked up in cpc counts
11/7/08 12:43:02 PM cpc counts way high still picking up drizzle
11/7/08 12:47:59 PM cpc counts way high still picking up drizzle
11/7/08 12:48:09 PM cpc counts way high still picking up drizzle
11/7/08 12:48:12 PM cpc counts way high still picking up drizzle
11/7/08 12:50:16 PM reduce pcasp flow
11/7/08 12:51:12 PM tip us now at 45 degrees
11/7/08 12:52:58 PM P plenu very high has it topped out?
11/7/08 12:55:07 PM P plenu very high has it topped out?
11/7/08 12:56:10 PM P plenu very high has it topped out?
11/7/08 12:56:55 PM into CVI mode, AMS switched to CVI
11/7/08 12:57:05 PM AMS set to negative flow = -0.2l/min
11/7/08 12:57:18 PM Lcontrol set to 0.2
11/7/08 12:57:24 PM counterflow is 1.35
11/7/08 12:57:48 PM total sample flow is reported as 1.33, this is incirrect, due to AMS negative flow
11/7/08 12:58:15 PM drizzle shTTERING
11/7/08 12:59:58 PM no TAS feed, no EF so can't telll any result at the minutew
11/7/08 1:00:54 PM use HORACE simulator to get the TAS for the EF
11/7/08 1:02:09 PM set TAS to 111m/s from Captain report
11/7/08 1:03:27 PM use the other feed from horace, tamb=285
11/7/08 1:03:35 PM pamb=882
11/7/08 1:05:46 PM remove horace simulator as HORACEW is giving TAS again
11/7/08 1:06:23 PM remove horace simulator as HORACEW is giving TAS again
11/7/08 1:07:26 PM remove horace simulator as HORACEW is giving TAS again
11/7/08 1:07:30 PM remove horace simulator as HORACEW is giving TAS again
11/7/08 1:07:36 PM cdp=20 rad=35
11/7/08 1:07:45 PM 2dc smal drizzle
11/7/08 1:09:09 PM we have a general increase in drops, but alll others are reporting the opposite
11/7/08 1:09:20 PM we have a general increase in drops, but alll others are reporting the opposite
11/7/08 1:09:23 PM we have a general increase in drops, but alll others are reporting the opposite

11/7/08 1:10:35 PM we have a general increase in drops, but all others are reporting the opposite

11/7/08 1:12:30 PM we saw an increase in drop number as others did

11/7/08 1:12:58 PM but no real increase in LWC, unless smoothing the signal will make the trend appear

11/7/08 1:18:35 PM plenum is much higher pressure at this altitude

11/7/08 1:22:11 PM AMS switching to rosemount,

11/7/08 1:22:23 PM CVI staying in aerosol

11/7/08 1:23:28 PM lag about 13 seconds to PCASP Lyman just after

11/7/08 1:23:55 PM lag about 13 seconds to PCASP Lyman just after

11/7/08 1:23:58 PM lag about 13 seconds to PCASP Lyman just after

11/7/08 1:24:01 PM lag about 13 seconds to PCASP Lyman just after

11/7/08 1:25:38 PM hotwire~0.6 on last saw

11/7/08 1:25:42 PM hotwire

11/7/08 1:25:47 PM we saw about 0.15

11/7/08 1:26:03 PM reduce counterflow using the ams countrol even though no ams sampling

11/7/08 1:26:19 PM use about -0.5 for this leg, as

11/7/08 1:27:35 PM still have a zero

11/7/08 1:27:50 PM bottom of cu cloud about 2.1kft

11/7/08 1:27:58 PM didnt see much

11/7/08 1:28:30 PM spike in particle concs at cu cloud level?

11/7/08 1:28:43 PM hitting main cloud base now

11/7/08 1:29:27 PM cpc climbing rapidly now

11/7/08 1:29:45 PM LWC not doing that much but it is rising a little

11/7/08 1:29:52 PM LWC not doing that much but it is rising a little

11/7/08 1:31:05 PM LWC not doing that much but it is rising a little

11/7/08 1:31:19 PM reduce AMS flow again try to see more of the cloud

11/7/08 1:31:47 PM back in cloud

11/7/08 1:32:48 PM difference in sampling capability climbing vs descending

11/7/08 1:33:25 PM below main cloud, still in scattered Cu

11/7/08 1:33:52 PM can see two layers in cloud on CPC trace in both directions

11/7/08 1:35:11 PM increase sample and counterflow air PID set points to 49.9

11/7/08 1:35:31 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:37:24 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:37:30 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:37:35 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:37:38 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:37:41 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:37:42 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:37:44 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:37:57 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:37:59 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:38:03 PM keep the tip temperature at 20 degrees

11/7/08 1:40:32 PM just about go a zero above cloud

11/7/08 1:41:43 PM the reverse situation on up-down legs this time - is it just non-uniformity of cloud

11/7/08 1:42:04 PM bouncy at cloud base

11/7/08 1:42:21 PM end of run

11/7/08 1:43:29 PM drizzle?

11/7/08 1:44:27 PM

11/7/08 1:44:51 PM reduce ams flow again to

11/7/08 1:45:34 PM flow has stabilised now

11/7/08 1:46:16 PM a decent zero on pcasp

11/7/08 1:50:29 PM cvi back into aerosol mode

11/7/08 2:02:58 PM cvi back into aerosol mode

11/7/08 2:04:07 PM cvi back into aerosol mode

11/7/08 2:04:42 PM cvi back into aerosol mode

11/7/08 2:05:38 PM mission three - AG says we went through some cirrus, we saw an increase in LWC

11/7/08 2:08:46 PM alter pcasp flows

11/7/08 3:06:00 PM alter pcasp flows

11/7/08 3:06:08 PM alter pcasp flows

11/7/08 3:06:51 PM put into counterflow mode for last cloud passage and rest of profile descent

11/7/08 3:08:25 PM put into counterflow mode for last cloud passage and rest of profile descent

11/7/08 3:08:26 PM put into counterflow mode for last cloud passage and rest of profile descent

11/7/08 3:08:29 PM put into counterflow mode for last cloud passage and rest of
profile descent
11/7/08 3:11:17 PM put into counterflow mode for last cloud passage and rest of
profile descent
11/7/08 3:11:21 PM put into counterflow mode for last cloud passage and rest of
profile descent
11/7/08 3:11:27 PM put into counterflow mode for last cloud passage and rest of
profile descent
11/7/08 3:11:31 PM put into counterflow mode for last cloud passage and rest of
profile descent
11/7/08 3:12:08 PM pcasp counts increasing now
11/7/08 3:16:15 PM counterflow ON
11/7/08 3:36:42 PM counterflow off, shut down

ARIES flight log

Flight: B416

page 1 of 2

Date: 07/Nov/2008 Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VOCALS POC

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0840	On the ground						Power on
084658	"		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot 1 min. script.
1030	TAKE OFF						
103220	FL				71	31	Take off → FL230
1053	↑FL180		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min Ci above
105814	FL220	RI			71	30	Sunde 1
105955	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min 8/8 JCR below
110413	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min Sunde 2
110826	"		N	O	71	30	Nadir Long Run 3 min
111214	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min Sunde 3
1118	"	240 x 1	N	O	71	31	Nadir
112014	"		Z	O	71	30	Zenith Long Run 3 min Sunde 4
112406	"		N	O	71	30	Nadir Long Run 3 min
112754	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min Sunde 5
113209	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min
1140			ast	←			Script lock-up at 99% done
114121			N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min.
115455	P ↓						
1215	FL049		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min
123119	P ↓		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot 1 min
123540	1000 ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nadir Zen Long Run 30 sec
1255	P ↑	EOR		C	71	31	to 3000 ft
132246	↓		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min
1342							Banking
1405			Z	O	71	30	Zenith Long Run 3 min Same Ci above
140743	FL230			O	70	31	Sunde 6
140916			N	O	71	30	Nadir Long Run 3 min
141333			Z	O	70	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min Same Ci above Sunde 7
141750			N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min
142204			Z	O	71	30	Zenith Long Run 3 min Sunde 8
142622			N	O	70	30	Nadir Long Run 3 min

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	7/11/08	Flight	B416	log pages
Operator(s)	Jeff Norwood-Brown		Campaign	Vocals		
Departure			Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	22.0°C	Ch 17	22.0°C	Ch18	21.5°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot	292.4	Cold	291.5		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					0853
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	Cold			
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

B416_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

08:33:21.04 --- - - - -
08:33:21.04 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:33:21.04 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:33:21.04 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. 416
08:33:21.04 --- - - - -
08:33:28.09 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:33:30.71 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
08:33:32.36 SWS 173.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:33:39.16 SWS - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:33:43.12 USH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:33:47.23 LSH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:33:48.64 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:33:48.73 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:33:48.91 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:33:51.09 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:33:55.93 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:33:55.93 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:33:57.62 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:33:59.92 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:33:59.93 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:34:01.60 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:34:04.56 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:34:04.57 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:34:06.56 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:34:06.56 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:34:06.56 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:34:29.22 USH - - - - Idling
08:34:29.28 SWS - - - - Idling
08:34:29.29 LSH - - - - Idling
08:34:30.75 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:34:35.15 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:34:38.86 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:34:38.86 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:34:38.88 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:34:39.38 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:34:40.29 SWS - - - - Idling
08:34:40.50 LSH - - - - Idling
08:34:40.70 USH - - - - Idling
09:24:09.89 --- - - - -
09:24:09.89 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:24:09.89 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:24:09.89 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. 416
09:24:09.89 --- - - - -
09:24:14.86 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
09:24:19.14 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
09:24:23.19 SWS - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:24:27.95 USH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:24:31.63 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:24:33.01 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:24:33.08 LSH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:24:34.65 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:24:36.84 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:24:38.96 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:24:40.85 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:24:44.96 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:24:44.96 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:24:48.48 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:24:48.48 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:24:51.75 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:24:51.75 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:24:55.56 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:24:55.56 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:24:55.57 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:25:36.13 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:25:36.24 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.

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09:25:36.28 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:25:36.45 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:25:37.61 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:25:37.76 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:25:37.97 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:25:38.75 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:25:41.96 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:25:45.16 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:25:48.37 USH - - - - Idling
09:25:48.44 SWS - - - - Idling
09:25:48.50 LSH - - - - Idling
09:25:50.16 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:25:50.17 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:25:50.18 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:25:50.73 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:25:51.62 USH - - - - Idling
09:25:51.87 LSH - - - - Idling
09:25:52.03 SWS - - - - Idling
09:29:40.05 --- - - - - *** 30 deg
09:30:12.01 --- - - - - *** peltiers not cooling box at the moment
have already restarted once
10:03:00.17 --- - - - -
10:03:00.17 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:03:00.17 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:03:00.17 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. 416
10:03:00.17 --- - - - -
10:03:04.50 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:03:07.24 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
10:03:09.31 SWS -0.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
10:03:09.87 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
10:03:10.21 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:03:10.31 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:03:10.74 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:03:11.84 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:03:19.69 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:03:21.56 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:03:21.57 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:03:22.66 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:03:24.83 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:03:24.83 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:03:25.93 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:03:27.32 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:03:27.32 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:03:29.16 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:03:29.16 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:03:29.17 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:03:47.22 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:03:51.45 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:03:51.46 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:03:51.50 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:03:52.91 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:03:53.10 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:03:53.31 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:03:54.79 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:03:54.81 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:03:54.81 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:03:56.23 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:03:56.57 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:03:56.73 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:45:00.20 --- - - - -
10:45:00.20 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:45:00.20 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:45:00.20 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. 416
10:45:00.20 --- - - - -
10:45:07.07 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:45:11.47 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:45:15.29 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK

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10:45:16.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:45:17.41	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:45:18.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:45:21.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
10:45:24.20	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:45:24.76	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:45:26.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:26.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:26.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:28.11	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:45:30.25	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
10:45:30.25	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
10:45:32.30	USH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:45:37.06	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
10:45:37.07	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
10:45:39.00	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:45:42.71	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:45:42.71	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:46:11.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:46:15.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:15.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:15.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:15.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:46:16.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:16.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:16.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:27.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** 32 deg
10:46:34.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** peltiers not working
10:46:59.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** LSH VI sin wave
10:47:08.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:08.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:08.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:09.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:47:09.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:10.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:10.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:51.69	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:51:53.41	SWS	172.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:52:05.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:05.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:05.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:05.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:52:05.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:52:06.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:52:06.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:06.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:07.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:08.01	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:52:11.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:11.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:11.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:12.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:52:12.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:12.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:13.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:31.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** all shutters working today
10:53:32.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** 30 deg
10:57:46.83	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:57:49.01	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:58:26.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at FL 230
10:58:34.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 1
10:58:38.91	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:58:43.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:43.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:43.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:44.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:58:44.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:45.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:45.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:58:47.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:47.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:47.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:47.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:58:48.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:48.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:48.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:16.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:59:16.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:59:16.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:59:18.27	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:59:19.96	SWS	172.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:59:20.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:20.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:20.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:23.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:23.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:23.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:23.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:59:24.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:24.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:25.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:32.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 28 deg
11:03:41.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** 27 deg
11:04:52.88	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:04:58.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:58.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:58.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:58.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:04:59.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:59.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:59.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:01.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:01.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:01.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:02.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:02.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:02.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:05.81	LSH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
11:05:05.82	LSH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
11:05:19.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:19.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:19.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:21.11	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:05:22.76	SWS	-0.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:05:24.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:24.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:24.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:26.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:26.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:26.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:26.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:05:27.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:27.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:27.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:33.25	LSH	-	-	5	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 5ms.
11:05:33.26	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 5ms.
11:05:39.31	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:05:39.31	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:05:48.07	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
11:05:48.08	LSH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
11:05:50.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:51.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:05:54.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:28.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 2
11:06:44.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 26 deg
11:06:52.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:52.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:52.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:06:53.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:53.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:06:53.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:56.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:58.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:58.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:58.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:59.94	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:07:01.62	SWS	171.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:07:03.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:03.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:03.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:02.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** 25 deg
11:12:51.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** no cirrus today just stratocumulus sheet
below						
11:12:59.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 24 deg
11:13:20.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:13:20.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:13:20.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:13:22.32	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:13:23.80	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:13:23.98	SWS	-1.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:13:28.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:28.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:28.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:31.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:31.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:31.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:32.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:32.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:13:32.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:33.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:13:35.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:36.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:30.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 3
11:14:46.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 24 deg
11:14:51.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:51.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:51.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:53.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:14:54.70	SWS	170.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:14:55.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:55.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:55.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:58.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:58.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:58.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:59.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:14:59.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:00.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:02.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:16:07.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** 23 deg
11:19:25.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 22 deg
11:20:41.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:20:41.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:20:41.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:20:41.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:20:41.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:20:42.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:20:44.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:47.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:47.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:47.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:49.24	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:21:50.88	SWS	-1.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:21:51.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:51.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:51.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:26.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 3

11:22:29.50	---	-	-	-	*** 21 deg
11:26:13.69	---	-	-	-	*** 20 deg
11:26:17.67	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:17.67	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:17.89	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:18.98	SWS	-6.0	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:26:20.66	SWS	171.4	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:26:21.75	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:21.75	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:21.75	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:24.42	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:24.46	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:24.50	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:24.95	LSH	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:26:25.39	USH	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:26:25.57	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:25.77	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:27.88	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:29.72	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:29.76	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:30.01	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:30.68	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:30.94	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:33.58	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:16.70	---	-	-	-	*** 20 deg
11:29:24.42	---	-	-	-	*** 19 deg
11:29:33.10	SWS	174.0	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:29:34.78	SWS	-3.0	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:30:28.43	---	-	-	-	*** sonde 4
11:30:42.39	---	-	-	-	*** LSH VIS working again now
11:30:45.41	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:30:45.42	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:30:45.56	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:30:47.35	SWS	-6.0	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:30:49.01	SWS	170.0	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:30:50.46	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:50.46	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:50.48	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:52.55	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:52.65	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:52.81	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:53.50	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:53.69	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:56.39	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:33:18.96	---	-	-	-	*** 18 deg
11:37:01.39	---	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
11:38:16.17	---	-	-	-	*** stratq sheet breaking up in places below
11:40:59.80	---	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
11:41:02.77	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:41:02.82	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:41:02.85	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:41:03.96	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:04.15	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:06.60	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:43.00	---	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:47:53.08	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:53.13	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:53.16	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:54.02	LSH	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:47:54.04	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:54.27	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:56.97	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:51:15.57	---	-	-	-	*** LSH fault is back
11:53:27.46	---	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:53:50.78	---	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:54:54.18	---	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
11:55:00.10	---	-	-	-	*** profile descent
11:57:28.57	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:28.58	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:57:28.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:29.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:57:29.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:29.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:32.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:07.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** in
12:00:32.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** POC region now
12:00:47.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 DEG
12:01:23.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 DEG
12:02:19.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:06:06.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:10:36.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile
12:11:25.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 2
12:12:43.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:13:06.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:13:16.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run now
12:14:19.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:18:31.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:31.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:32.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:32.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:33.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:35.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:38.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:38.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:38.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:39.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:39.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:41.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:46.56	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
12:18:46.56	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
12:18:51.36	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
12:18:51.36	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
12:18:54.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:54.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:54.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:54.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:55.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:55.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:56.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:00.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:02.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:02.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:02.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:03.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:03.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:03.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:05.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:05.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:05.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:06.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:06.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:07.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:13.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:25:10.60	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:25:14.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:25:15.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:25:15.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:25:16.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:16.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:16.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:19.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:25:19.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:25:19.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:25:21.60	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:25:23.33	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:25:24.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:24.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:24.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:25:27.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:25:27.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:25:27.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:25:28.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:28.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:28.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:21.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:26:21.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:26:21.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:26:21.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:26:23.03	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:26:24.78	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:26:25.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:25.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:25.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:29.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:29.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:29.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:30.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:30.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:30.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:31.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:26:43.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
12:26:50.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:16.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:31:20.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending
12:32:36.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4300 ft
12:33:34.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud bottom 3000 ft
12:35:24.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
12:35:29.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:29.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:29.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:31.36	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:35:33.09	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:35:33.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:33.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:33.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:39.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:39.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:39.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:40.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:40.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:40.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:55.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3 below cloud
12:36:02.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:02.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:02.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:03.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:03.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:04.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:02.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** intermittent drizzle
12:42:33.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** hole in cloud
12:51:06.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:06.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:06.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:07.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:07.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:08.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:12.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:12.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:12.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:13.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:13.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:14.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:20.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:20.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:20.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:22.59	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:51:24.29	SWS	172.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

12:51:25.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:25.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:25.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:43.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:43.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:43.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:45.03	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:51:46.75	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:51:47.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:47.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:47.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:55.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
12:55:31.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:55:40.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to 3000 ft
12:58:04.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
12:58:09.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
12:58:30.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** edging up yo 3900 ft
13:01:32.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:32.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:32.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:33.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:34.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:34.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:36.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:36.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:36.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:37.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:37.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:38.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:07.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:07.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:07.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:12.74	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:04:14.45	SWS	172.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:04:15.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:15.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:15.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:17.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:17.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:17.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:18.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:18.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:19.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:40.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:09:45.86	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:09:47.60	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:09:49.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:49.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:49.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:50.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:51.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:51.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:41.11	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:13:42.84	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:13:43.16	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:13:45.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:45.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:45.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:45.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:46.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:46.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:46.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:17.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:23.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:23.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:23.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:24.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:25.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:25.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

13:20:13.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:22:05.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4500 ft
13:22:26.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** reverse sdaw tooth
13:22:54.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:22:54.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:22:54.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:22:55.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:22:55.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:22:55.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:05.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4500 ft
13:24:11.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:24:41.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 2800 ft
13:24:43.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:43.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:44.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:44.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:45.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:45.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:07.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:25:07.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:25:07.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:25:09.73	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:25:11.47	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:25:12.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:12.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:12.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:13.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:13.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:13.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:14.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:15.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:15.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:26:11.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** reverse sawtooth
13:28:24.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** cb 2100 ft
13:30:12.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top
13:30:19.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4500 ft
13:30:39.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** some cirrus above
13:30:57.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** reverse
13:30:59.91	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:31:01.59	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:31:03.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:03.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:03.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:04.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:04.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:05.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:44.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top
13:33:03.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud bottom
13:33:33.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:33.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:33.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:34.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:34.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:35.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:35.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:38.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:38.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:41.46	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:33:43.14	SWS	-3.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:33:43.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:43.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:43.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:45.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:45.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:45.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:46.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:46.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:47.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:51.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** scatered cloud base at 2000 ft

13:35:26.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** reversing
13:35:47.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** from 1000 ft
13:40:22.93	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:40:24.65	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:40:26.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:26.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:26.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:27.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:27.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:28.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:24.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** run ended
13:42:50.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:50.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:51.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:52.60	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:42:54.27	SWS	-2.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:42:55.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:55.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:55.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:58.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:58.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:58.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:59.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:59.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:59.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:44:23.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb from 1000 ft profile 6
13:48:23.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** leaving cloud now
13:48:36.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4200 ft
13:48:43.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:43.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:43.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:45.82	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:48:47.56	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:48:48.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:48.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:48.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:50.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:50.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:50.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:50.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:48:51.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:51.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:51.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:36.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
14:02:28.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:28.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:28.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:29.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:02:29.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:29.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:30.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:47.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** some cirrus above
14:07:44.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p climb start of run
14:07:46.98	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:07:48.64	SWS	-3.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:07:52.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde
14:08:01.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** number 6
14:09:07.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:07.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:07.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:08.88	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:09:10.63	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:09:11.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:11.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:11.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:13.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:13.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:13.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:14.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

14:09:14.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:14.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:15.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:41.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:14:41.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:14:41.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:14:43.67	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:14:45.33	SWS	-1.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:14:46.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:46.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:46.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:47.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:47.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:47.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:48.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:14:48.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:48.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:49.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:50.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:50.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:50.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:51.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:51.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:52.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:44.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 7
14:16:42.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:42.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:43.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:44.99	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:16:46.67	SWS	172.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:16:47.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:47.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:47.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:49.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:49.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:49.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:50.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:16:50.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:50.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:51.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:04.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:17:04.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:17:04.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:17:04.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:17:05.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:05.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:05.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:57.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:57.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:57.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:59.33	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:23:01.06	SWS	-5.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:23:03.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:03.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:03.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:05.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:05.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:05.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:05.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:23:06.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:06.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:06.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:45.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 8
14:24:01.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:01.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:01.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:02.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:24:02.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:02.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:24:03.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:04.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:04.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:04.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:06.27	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:24:08.02	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:24:08.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:08.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:08.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:11.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:11.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:11.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:11.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:24:11.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:12.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:12.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:31:40.55	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:31:42.32	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:31:46.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde
14:31:48.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:31:48.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:31:48.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:31:49.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:31:49.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:31:49.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:31:50.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:13.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:34:13.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:34:13.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:34:15.67	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:34:17.41	SWS	173.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:34:19.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:19.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:19.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:27.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:27.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:27.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:28.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:35:28.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:29.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:29.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:40:43.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:40:43.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:40:43.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:40:45.42	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:40:47.17	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:40:47.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:40:47.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:40:47.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:16.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde
14:41:23.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:23.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:23.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:23.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:41:23.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:24.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:24.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:26.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:26.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:26.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:28.38	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:41:30.15	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:41:31.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:31.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:31.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:33.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:33.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:33.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:33.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

14:41:34.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:34.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:34.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:29.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:29.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:29.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:29.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:46:29.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:30.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:30.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:33.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:33.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:33.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:34.60	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:46:36.34	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:46:37.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:37.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:37.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:40.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:40.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:40.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:40.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:46:41.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:41.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:41.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:00.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde
14:48:13.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:13.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:13.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:16.63	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:48:18.34	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:48:21.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:21.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:21.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:24.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:24.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:24.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:24.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:48:25.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:25.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:25.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:00.95	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:55:07.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:07.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:07.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:08.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:55:08.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:08.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:09.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:14.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:14.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:14.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:14.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:55:14.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:15.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:15.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:15.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:15.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:15.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:21.09	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:58:22.83	SWS	-5.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:58:23.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:23.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:23.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:25.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:25.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:25.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:26.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:58:26.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:58:27.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:27.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:31.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:31.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:31.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:31.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:58:32.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:32.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:33.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:40.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
14:59:22.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:59:31.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile desecnt
14:59:37.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:59:37.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:59:37.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:59:39.67	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:59:41.42	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:59:42.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:42.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:42.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:44.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:59:44.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:59:44.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:59:44.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:59:45.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:45.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:45.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:34.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:35.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:42.95	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
15:00:42.97	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
15:00:44.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:45.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:46.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:47.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:48.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:49.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:34.33	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:11:39.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:39.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:39.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:39.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:11:40.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:40.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:40.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:48.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:48.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:48.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:50.91	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:16:52.64	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:16:53.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:53.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:53.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:55.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:55.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:56.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:56.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:16:56.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:57.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:57.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:17:00.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:17:00.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:17:00.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:17:01.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:17:01.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:17:01.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:17:02.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:18.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:22:42.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.

15:24:42.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:34:01.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:01.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:01.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:02.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:34:02.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:03.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:03.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

b416 lwc PROFILE 3

b416 lwc PROFILE RUN 4

b416 lwc RUN 4

B416 tephi P1

B416 tephi P7

B416 heimann run 6 hi level

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B416:

Log	Reason
Instrument Status	may not be correct – Flight Manager asked to check
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
PAN log	PAN operator does not create a log sheet
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	16 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_102859_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_112859_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_122859_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_132859_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_142859_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_152859_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_102840_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_112840_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_122840_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_132840_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_142840_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_152840_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_102848_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_112848_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_122848_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_132848_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_142848_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_152848_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_102854_1hz.av
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_112854_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_122854_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_132854_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_142854_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081107_r0_b416_152854_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.